

Rec(over)y

a sonata for bass clarinet and piano

Dalton H. Regnier

I. Repetition/Tension

frantic $\text{♩} = \text{c. } 112$

Bass Clarinet

Piano

f

f

4

p

8

ff

12

Musical score for measures 12-13. The score is written for three staves: Treble, Piano, and Bass. Measure 12 is in 3/4 time, and measure 13 is in 4/4 time. The Treble staff contains rests in both measures. The Piano staff features a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, including slurs and accents. The Bass staff provides harmonic support with chords and single notes, also featuring slurs and accents.

14

Musical score for measures 14-15. The score is written for three staves: Treble, Piano, and Bass. Measure 14 is in 3/4 time, and measure 15 is in 4/4 time. The Treble staff contains rests in both measures. The Piano staff features a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, including slurs and accents. The Bass staff provides harmonic support with chords and single notes, also featuring slurs and accents.

17

Musical score for measures 17-18. The score is written for three staves: Treble, Piano, and Bass. Measure 17 is in 4/4 time, and measure 18 is in 3/4 time. The Treble staff contains rests in both measures. The Piano staff features a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, including slurs and accents. The Bass staff provides harmonic support with chords and single notes, also featuring slurs and accents.

19

Musical score for measures 19-21. The score is written for three staves: a single treble staff at the top, and a grand staff (treble and bass) below. Measure 19 is in 7/8 time, measure 20 in 3/4, and measure 21 in 4/4. The music features complex rhythmic patterns and dynamic markings such as *v* and *8va*.

22

Musical score for measures 22-24. The score is written for three staves. Measure 22 is in 4/4 time, measure 23 in 3/4, and measure 24 in 4/4. A box labeled 'A' is placed above the first staff in measure 23. Dynamic markings include *ff* and *f*. The music features complex rhythmic patterns and dynamic markings such as *v*.

25

Musical score for measures 25-28. The score is written for three staves. Measure 25 is in 3/8 time, measure 26 in 2/4, measure 27 in 3/4, and measure 28 in 2/4. Dynamic markings include *p sub.*, *molto*, and *ff*. The music features complex rhythmic patterns and dynamic markings such as *v*.

29

Musical score for measures 29-31. The piece is in 3/4 time. Measure 29 features a complex melodic line in the right hand with many accidentals (sharps and naturals) and slurs. The left hand is mostly silent. Measure 30 shows a change to 2/4 time, with the right hand continuing its melodic line and the left hand entering with a bass line. Measure 31 is in 3/4 time, with a final chord in the left hand marked with a *v.* (accents) and a fermata.

32

Musical score for measures 32-34. Measure 32 is in 3/4 time, with a melodic line in the right hand and a bass line in the left hand. Measure 33 is in 7/8 time, with a change in the right hand's melodic pattern. Measure 34 is in 3/4 time, ending with a final chord in the left hand marked with a *v.* and a fermata.

35

Musical score for measures 35-36. Measure 35 is in 5/4 time, featuring a melodic line in the right hand and a bass line in the left hand. A dynamic marking *p sub.* is written below the right hand, and a crescendo hairpin leads to a *ff* marking. Measure 36 is in 4/4 time, with a final chord in the left hand marked with a *v.* and a fermata.

37

4/4 3/4 4/4

40

4/4 7/8 4/4 3/4

p *ff sub.* *p*

p *f* *p*

44

3/4 7/8 3/4

ff *f*

47

50

54

B uneasy

58

Musical score for measures 58-62. The piece is in 4/4 time. The upper staff (treble clef) has whole rests for measures 58-61 and a melodic phrase in measure 62 starting on G4, moving to F4, E4, D4, C4, and ending on B3. The lower staff (bass clef) has whole rests for measures 58-61 and a bass line in measure 62 starting on G2, moving to F2, E2, D2, C2, and ending on B1. Dynamics include *f* in the upper staff and *mp* in the lower staff.

63

Musical score for measures 63-66. The upper staff (treble clef) features a melodic line with slurs and accents, moving from G4 down to B3. Dynamics include *ff* and *pp sub. <*. The lower staff (bass clef) has a bass line with slurs and accents, moving from G2 down to B1.

67

Musical score for measures 67-70. The upper staff (treble clef) has a melodic line starting on G4, moving to F4, E4, D4, C4, and ending on B3. Dynamics include *f*. The lower staff (bass clef) has a bass line with slurs and accents, moving from G2 down to B1.

71

Musical score for measures 71-74. The score is in treble and bass clefs. Measure 71 has a whole rest in the treble and a quarter note G4 in the bass. Measure 72 has a whole rest in the treble and a quarter note A4 in the bass. Measure 73 has a whole rest in the treble and a quarter note B4 in the bass. Measure 74 has a treble clef with a quarter note B4, quarter note C5, quarter note D5, and quarter note E5, all beamed together with a fermata and an accent (>). The bass clef has a quarter note D4, quarter note E4, quarter note F4, and quarter note G4, all beamed together. The dynamic is *f*. Time signatures are 3/4 and 4/4.

75

Musical score for measures 75-78. The score is in treble and bass clefs. Measure 75 has a treble clef with a triplet of quarter notes G4, A4, B4, and a triplet of quarter notes C5, B4, A4, all with accents (>). The dynamic is *ff sub.*. The bass clef has a quarter note G4. Measure 76 has a whole rest in the treble and a quarter note G4 in the bass. Measure 77 has a treble clef with a quarter note B4, quarter note C5, quarter note D5, and quarter note E5, all beamed together with a fermata and an accent (>). The dynamic is *f*. The bass clef has a quarter note G4, quarter note A4, quarter note B4, and quarter note C5, all beamed together. Measure 78 has a treble clef with a quarter note B4, quarter note C5, quarter note D5, and quarter note E5, all beamed together with a fermata and an accent (>). The dynamic is *f*. The bass clef has a quarter note G4, quarter note A4, quarter note B4, and quarter note C5, all beamed together. Time signatures are 3/4 and 4/4.

79

Musical score for measures 79-82. The score is in treble and bass clefs. Measure 79 has a treble clef with a quarter note G4, quarter note A4, quarter note B4, and quarter note C5, all beamed together with a fermata and an accent (>). The dynamic is *ff*. The bass clef has a quarter note G4, quarter note A4, quarter note B4, and quarter note C5, all beamed together. Measure 80 has a treble clef with a quarter note B4, quarter note C5, quarter note D5, and quarter note E5, all beamed together with a fermata and an accent (>). The dynamic is *ff*. The bass clef has a quarter note G4, quarter note A4, quarter note B4, and quarter note C5, all beamed together. Measure 81 has a whole rest in the treble and a quarter note G4 in the bass. Measure 82 has a treble clef with a quarter note B4, quarter note C5, quarter note D5, and quarter note E5, all beamed together with a fermata and an accent (>). The dynamic is *f*. The bass clef has a quarter note G4, quarter note A4, quarter note B4, and quarter note C5, all beamed together. Time signatures are 2/4 and 4/4.

83 C

Musical score for measures 83-86. The score is in 4/4 time. Measure 83 features a treble clef staff with a melodic line of eighth notes, some with slurs and accents, and a bass clef staff with a steady eighth-note accompaniment. Measure 84 has a treble clef staff with a whole rest and a bass clef staff with eighth notes. Measure 85 has a treble clef staff with a whole rest and a bass clef staff with eighth notes, including a *mf* dynamic marking. Measure 86 has a treble clef staff with a whole rest and a bass clef staff with eighth notes.

87

Musical score for measures 87-89. The score is in 4/4 time. Measure 87 features a treble clef staff with a melodic line of eighth notes, some with slurs and accents, and a bass clef staff with eighth notes. Measure 88 has a treble clef staff with a whole rest and a bass clef staff with eighth notes. Measure 89 has a treble clef staff with a whole rest and a bass clef staff with eighth notes, including a *ff sub.* dynamic marking.

90

Musical score for measures 90-92. The score is in 4/4 time. Measure 90 features a treble clef staff with a melodic line of eighth notes, some with slurs and accents, and a bass clef staff with eighth notes. Measure 91 has a treble clef staff with a whole rest and a bass clef staff with eighth notes. Measure 92 has a treble clef staff with a whole rest and a bass clef staff with eighth notes, including a *mf* dynamic marking.

93

Musical score for measures 93-96. The score is in 4/4 time. Measure 93 features a complex piano accompaniment with sixteenth-note patterns in the right hand and eighth-note patterns in the left hand. Measures 94-96 show a melodic line in the right hand with slurs and accents, and a bass line in the left hand with eighth-note patterns. The key signature has one sharp (F#).

97

Musical score for measures 97-100. The score is in 4/4 time. Measure 97 continues the melodic line from the previous system. Measures 98-100 feature a piano accompaniment with triplets in both hands, marked with *f*. A dynamic marking of *p sub.* is present in measure 100. An 8va marking is shown above the right hand in measure 100. The key signature has one sharp (F#).

101

D

Musical score for measures 101-104. The score is in 4/4 time. Measure 101 features a piano accompaniment with a melodic line in the right hand, marked with *mf*. A dynamic marking of *mf* is present. A box containing the letter 'D' is located above the first staff. Measures 102-104 show a melodic line in the right hand with slurs and accents, and a bass line in the left hand with eighth-note patterns. A wavy line above the right hand in measure 102 is labeled "teeth on reed". The key signature has one sharp (F#).

105

Musical score for measures 105-108. The score is in 3/4, 2/4, and 4/4 time signatures. It features a vocal line and a piano accompaniment. The piano part includes a triplet of eighth notes in the right hand and a triplet of eighth notes in the left hand, both marked *ff sub.* in measure 106. The dynamic *mf* is indicated in measure 107. The vocal line has a slur over measures 105 and 108.

109

Musical score for measures 109-112. The score is in 3/4, 5/8, and 4/4 time signatures. It features a vocal line and a piano accompaniment. The piano part includes a triplet of eighth notes in the right hand and a triplet of eighth notes in the left hand, both marked *fp* in measure 109. The dynamic *ff* is indicated in measure 110. The vocal line has a slur over measures 109 and 112.

113

Musical score for measures 113-116. The score is in 3/4, 2/4, and 2/4 time signatures. It features a vocal line and a piano accompaniment. The piano part includes a quintuplet of eighth notes in the right hand and a sextuplet of eighth notes in the left hand, both marked *ff* in measure 113. The vocal line has a slur over measures 113 and 116.

teeth on reed,
as strident as possible

117

f possibile

122

f *p*

125

E

ff sub.

128

Musical score for measures 128-131. The score is in 3/4 time. The piano part consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The treble staff contains a melodic line with notes and rests. The bass staff contains a bass line with notes and rests. Dynamics include *p sub.* and *ff sub.*. The music shows a progression of chords and melodic fragments.

132

Musical score for measures 132-136. The score is in 3/4 time. The piano part consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The treble staff contains a melodic line with notes and rests. The bass staff contains a bass line with notes and rests. The music shows a progression of chords and melodic fragments.

137

Musical score for measures 137-140. The score is in 3/4 time. The piano part consists of a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The treble staff contains a melodic line with notes and rests. The bass staff contains a bass line with notes and rests. The music shows a progression of chords and melodic fragments.

141

8va

p sub.

144

F

f *p sub.* *f* *p sub.* *mf* **3**

149

f

152

tr

p sub.

f

156

160

163

Musical score for measures 163-166. The system consists of three staves: a single treble staff at the top and a grand staff (treble and bass) below. The top staff begins with a treble clef, a key signature of one flat (B-flat), and a 4/4 time signature. It features a melodic line with a long slur spanning measures 163 and 164, and a fermata over the final note in measure 166. The grand staff below has a treble clef and a bass clef. The bass line is highly rhythmic, featuring eighth and sixteenth notes with frequent accents (v) and slurs. The treble line of the grand staff contains chords and single notes, also with accents and slurs. The time signature changes from 4/4 to 3/4 in measure 164, then to 2/4 in measure 165, and finally to 3/4 in measure 166.

167

Musical score for measures 167-170. The system consists of three staves: a single treble staff at the top and a grand staff (treble and bass) below. The top staff begins with a treble clef, a key signature of one flat (B-flat), and a 4/4 time signature. It features a melodic line with a long slur spanning measures 167 and 168, and a fermata over the final note in measure 170. The grand staff below has a treble clef and a bass clef. The bass line is highly rhythmic, featuring eighth and sixteenth notes with frequent accents (v) and slurs. The treble line of the grand staff contains chords and single notes, also with accents and slurs. The time signature changes from 4/4 to 3/4 in measure 168, then to 2/4 in measure 169, and finally to 3/4 in measure 170.

171

Musical score for measures 171-174. The system consists of three staves: a single treble staff at the top and a grand staff (treble and bass) below. The top staff begins with a treble clef, a key signature of one flat (B-flat), and a 4/4 time signature. It features a melodic line with a long slur spanning measures 171 and 172, and a fermata over the final note in measure 174. The grand staff below has a treble clef and a bass clef. The bass line is highly rhythmic, featuring eighth and sixteenth notes with frequent accents (v) and slurs. The treble line of the grand staff contains chords and single notes, also with accents and slurs. The time signature changes from 4/4 to 3/4 in measure 173, then to 2/4 in measure 174.

174

Musical score for measures 174-176. The system includes a vocal line and a piano accompaniment. The piano part features a complex rhythmic pattern with many sixteenth notes and rests, marked with accents (v). The key signature has one flat (B-flat), and the time signature is 3/4. A dynamic marking of *ff* (fortissimo) is present in the piano part. The vocal line has a fermata over the first measure.

177

Musical score for measures 177-181. The system includes a vocal line and a piano accompaniment. The piano part continues with the complex rhythmic pattern, marked with accents (v). A dynamic marking of *mf* (mezzo-forte) is present in the piano part. A box labeled 'G' is placed above the piano part in measure 180. The vocal line has a fermata over the first measure and a sharp sign (#) above the final note in measure 181.

182

Musical score for measures 182-185. The system includes a vocal line and a piano accompaniment. The piano part continues with the complex rhythmic pattern, marked with accents (v). The vocal line has a sharp sign (#) above the first note in measure 182 and a flat sign (b) above the final note in measure 185.

186

Musical score for measures 186-189. The top staff is a single melodic line with a long slur. The middle and bottom staves are piano accompaniment with chords and moving lines. Dynamics include *ff*.

190

Musical score for measures 190-193. The top staff has rests followed by a melodic phrase. The middle staff has piano accompaniment with rests and a dynamic marking of *mp*. The bottom staff continues the piano accompaniment. Time signatures change from 2/4 to 3/4.

194

Musical score for measures 194-197. The top staff has a melodic line with slurs. The middle staff has rests. The bottom staff has piano accompaniment. Time signatures change from 2/4 to 3/4.

198

Musical score for measures 198-202. The score is in 3/4 time with a key signature of two flats. It features a treble clef staff with a melodic line and a grand staff (bass and piano) with a complex accompaniment. The piano part has a *ff* dynamic marking in measure 202.

203

Musical score for measures 203-206. The score is in 3/4 time with a key signature of two flats. It features a treble clef staff with a melodic line and a grand staff (bass and piano) with a complex accompaniment. The piano part has a *mf* dynamic marking in measure 203.

207

H

Musical score for measures 207-211. The score is in 3/4 time with a key signature of two flats. It features a treble clef staff with a melodic line and a grand staff (bass and piano) with a complex accompaniment. The piano part has a *mf* dynamic marking in measure 207. A box labeled **H** is placed above the first measure of the treble staff.

211

Musical score for measures 211-214. The system includes a vocal line and a piano accompaniment. The vocal line features a melodic phrase with a slur and a fermata over the final note. The piano accompaniment consists of a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes in the left hand and rests in the right hand.

215

Musical score for measures 215-219. The system includes a vocal line and a piano accompaniment. The piano accompaniment is marked *ff* and features a complex rhythmic pattern with many accents. The vocal line has rests in measures 215-217 and then a melodic phrase in measures 218-219.

220

Musical score for measures 220-223. The system includes a vocal line and a piano accompaniment. The vocal line is marked *f* and features a melodic phrase with a slur. The piano accompaniment is marked *mf* and features a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes in the left hand and rests in the right hand.

224

Musical score for measures 224-226. The piece is in 2/4 time, with a key signature of one flat (B-flat). Measure 224 features a melodic line in the right hand starting with a half note G4, followed by a quarter note A4, and a half note B-flat4. The left hand plays a bass line of quarter notes: B-flat3, A3, G3, F3. Measure 225 continues the melodic line with a quarter note G4, a quarter note A4, and a half note B-flat4. The bass line continues with quarter notes: F3, E3, D3, C3. Measure 226 concludes the melodic line with a quarter note G4, a quarter note A4, and a half note B-flat4. The bass line continues with quarter notes: B-flat3, A3, G3, F3.

227

Musical score for measures 227-230. The piece is in 2/4 time, with a key signature of one flat (B-flat). Measure 227 features a melodic line in the right hand starting with a half note G4, followed by a quarter note A4, and a half note B-flat4. The left hand plays a bass line of quarter notes: B-flat3, A3, G3, F3. Measure 228 continues the melodic line with a quarter note G4, a quarter note A4, and a half note B-flat4. The bass line continues with quarter notes: F3, E3, D3, C3. Measure 229 features a melodic line in the right hand starting with a half note G4, followed by a quarter note A4, and a half note B-flat4. The left hand plays a bass line of quarter notes: B-flat3, A3, G3, F3. Measure 230 concludes the melodic line with a quarter note G4, a quarter note A4, and a half note B-flat4. The bass line continues with quarter notes: F3, E3, D3, C3. The dynamic marking *ff* (fortissimo) is present in measure 229.

I

231

Musical score for measures 231-234. The piece is in 3/4 time, with a key signature of one flat (B-flat). Measure 231 features a melodic line in the right hand starting with a half note G4, followed by a quarter note A4, and a half note B-flat4. The left hand plays a bass line of quarter notes: B-flat3, A3, G3, F3. Measure 232 continues the melodic line with a quarter note G4, a quarter note A4, and a half note B-flat4. The bass line continues with quarter notes: F3, E3, D3, C3. Measure 233 features a melodic line in the right hand starting with a half note G4, followed by a quarter note A4, and a half note B-flat4. The left hand plays a bass line of quarter notes: B-flat3, A3, G3, F3. Measure 234 concludes the melodic line with a quarter note G4, a quarter note A4, and a half note B-flat4. The bass line continues with quarter notes: F3, E3, D3, C3. The dynamic marking *ff* (fortissimo) is present in measure 231.

235

239

244

248

teeth on reed, as
strident as possible

J even more frantic $\text{♩} = 132$

253

p cresc. *mp* *mf*

255

f

257

ff

259

rit.....a tempo

261

266

like a wash of sound, does not need to line up with the bass clarinet

268

270

II. Rest

at peace, nearly frozen in time $\text{♩} = 48$

Bass Clarinet

Musical score for Bass Clarinet and Piano, measures 1-5. The Bass Clarinet part is in 4/4 time and features a series of rests followed by a melodic phrase starting in measure 5. The Piano part consists of a steady accompaniment of chords and single notes. Dynamics include *pp* and *p*.

6

Musical score for Bass Clarinet and Piano, measures 6-10. The Bass Clarinet part continues with a melodic line. The Piano part maintains its accompaniment. Dynamics include *pp sim.*

11

Musical score for Bass Clarinet and Piano, measures 11-15. The Bass Clarinet part has a melodic phrase. The Piano part includes an 8va marking for the right hand in measures 13-15. Dynamics include *pp*.

15

A

7 8va 7 8va 7 8va 7 8va p

19

24

B

28

Musical score for measures 28-31. The top staff (treble clef) contains whole rests. The middle staff (treble clef) features a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, including two triplet markings. The bottom staff (bass clef) provides a harmonic accompaniment with chords and moving lines.

32

Musical score for measures 32-36. A box labeled 'C' is positioned above the first measure of this system. The top staff (treble clef) contains a melodic line with slurs and dynamic markings *p* and *pp*. The middle staff (treble clef) and bottom staff (bass clef) provide harmonic accompaniment with chords and moving lines.

37

Musical score for measures 37-41. The top staff (treble clef) contains a melodic line with slurs and a dynamic marking *p*. The middle staff (treble clef) and bottom staff (bass clef) provide harmonic accompaniment with chords and moving lines.

42

Musical score for measures 42-45. The system consists of three staves: a vocal line (top) and a piano accompaniment (bottom two). The vocal line contains whole rests for all four measures. The piano accompaniment features a complex rhythmic pattern with eighth and sixteenth notes, and chords in the bass line.

46

D

Musical score for measures 46-49. The system consists of three staves. A box labeled 'D' is positioned above the vocal staff in measure 47. The vocal line has whole rests in measures 46 and 47, followed by a melodic phrase in measures 48 and 49. The piano accompaniment continues with a rhythmic accompaniment.

50

Musical score for measures 50-53. The system consists of three staves. The vocal line begins in measure 50 with a melodic phrase. The piano accompaniment provides a harmonic and rhythmic foundation with chords and a steady eighth-note accompaniment.

53

Musical score for measures 53-55. The top staff (treble clef) features a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, including a triplet of eighth notes. The bottom staff (grand staff) provides a piano accompaniment with chords and single notes.

56

E

Musical score for measures 56-59. The top staff (treble clef) features a melodic line with a fermata over the final note. The bottom staff (grand staff) provides a piano accompaniment. A box labeled "E" is positioned above the top staff.

60

Musical score for measures 60-63. The top staff (treble clef) features a melodic line with a fermata over the final note. The bottom staff (grand staff) provides a piano accompaniment.

F frustratingly

64

Musical score for measures 64-67. The system includes a vocal line and a piano accompaniment. The piano part features a complex texture with multiple voices in both hands, including sixteenth-note patterns and chords. The vocal line begins in measure 65 with a melodic phrase. Dynamics include *mp* (mezzo-piano) and *mp* (mezzo-piano).

68

Musical score for measures 68-71. The system includes a vocal line and a piano accompaniment. The piano part features a complex texture with multiple voices in both hands, including sixteenth-note patterns and chords. The vocal line continues with a melodic phrase. Dynamics include *mf* (mezzo-forte).

72

Musical score for measures 72-75. The system includes a vocal line and a piano accompaniment. The piano part features a complex texture with multiple voices in both hands, including sixteenth-note patterns and chords. The vocal line continues with a melodic phrase. Dynamics include *f* (forte).

75

Musical score for measures 75-76. The system consists of a treble clef staff and a grand staff (bass clef with two staves). Measure 75 features a complex melodic line in the treble with many accidentals and a triplet of eighth notes. The grand staff provides a rhythmic accompaniment with eighth notes and chords. Measure 76 continues the melodic development with a triplet of eighth notes.

77

Musical score for measures 77-79. Measure 77 begins with a **ff** dynamic marking and a triplet of eighth notes. The melodic line in the treble is highly active with many accidentals. The grand staff accompaniment consists of eighth notes and chords. Measures 78 and 79 continue the melodic and harmonic progression.

80

Musical score for measures 80-82. Measure 80 features a **ff** dynamic marking and a septuplet of eighth notes. A box containing the letter 'G' is positioned above the treble staff. The melodic line in the treble is complex with many accidentals. The grand staff accompaniment includes eighth notes and chords. Measures 81 and 82 continue the piece.

84

84

85

86

fff

mf

mf

mf

mf

mf

87

87

88

89

90

91

91

92

93

94

95

Musical score for measures 95-97. The system includes a vocal line and a piano accompaniment. The vocal line is mostly rests. The piano accompaniment features a right hand with sixteenth-note patterns and a left hand with chords and sixteenth-note accompaniment. Dynamics include *ff* and *gva*. There are also accents (*v*) and slurs.

98

Musical score for measures 98-101. The system includes a vocal line and a piano accompaniment. The vocal line has a few notes in measure 101. The piano accompaniment continues with similar patterns. Dynamics include *pp*. There are also accents (*v*) and slurs.

102

H at peace

Musical score for measures 102-105. The system includes a vocal line and a piano accompaniment. The vocal line has a melodic line starting with a sharp sign. The piano accompaniment features chords and sixteenth-note accompaniment. Dynamics include *ppp*. There are also slurs.

107

Musical score for measures 107-110. The system consists of three staves: a single treble clef staff at the top, and a grand staff (treble and bass clefs) below. The music is in a key with two sharps (F# and C#) and a 3/4 time signature. Measure 107 features a melodic line in the treble staff with eighth and quarter notes, and a piano accompaniment in the grand staff with chords and eighth notes. Measure 108 continues the melodic line with a half note and quarter note. Measure 109 has a melodic line with a quarter note and a half note. Measure 110 concludes with a melodic line ending on a half note and a piano accompaniment with a final chord.

111

Musical score for measures 111-115. The system consists of three staves: a single treble clef staff at the top, and a grand staff (treble and bass clefs) below. Measure 111 features a melodic line with a half note and quarter note, and a piano accompaniment with chords. Measure 112 has a melodic line with a half note and quarter note. Measure 113 has a melodic line with a half note and quarter note. Measure 114 has a melodic line with a half note and quarter note, and a piano accompaniment with a *rit.* marking. Measure 115 concludes with a melodic line ending on a half note and a piano accompaniment with a final chord.

116

Musical score for measures 116-120. The system consists of three staves: a single treble clef staff at the top, and a grand staff (treble and bass clefs) below. Measure 116 features a melodic line with a half note and quarter note, and a piano accompaniment with chords. Measure 117 has a melodic line with a half note and quarter note. Measure 118 has a melodic line with a half note and quarter note. Measure 119 has a melodic line with a half note and quarter note. Measure 120 concludes with a melodic line ending on a half note and a piano accompaniment with a final chord.

III. Reinvigoration

joyful ♩ = 112

Bass Clarinet

Piano

tr

tr

p

p

6

9

cresc. poco a poco

cresc. poco a poco

A

12

f p sub.

tr

pp

f

18

f

mf

21

f

24

Musical score for measures 24-26. The score is in 4/4 time. Measure 24 features a melodic line in the treble clef with a long slur over a half note and a fermata, and a piano accompaniment in the bass clef with eighth notes. Measure 25 continues the piano accompaniment. Measure 26 has a dynamic marking of *f* and features a change in the piano accompaniment to a more active eighth-note pattern.

27

B

Musical score for measures 27-29. Measure 27 is a whole rest in the treble clef. Measure 28 starts with a dynamic marking of *f* and features a melodic line in the treble clef with eighth notes and a slur. Measure 29 continues the melodic line. The piano accompaniment in the bass clef consists of eighth notes throughout. Measure 28 has a dynamic marking of *mf*.

30

Musical score for measures 30-32. Measure 30 is in 7/8 time and features a melodic line in the treble clef with eighth notes and a slur. Measure 31 is in 4/4 time and continues the melodic line. Measure 32 is in 4/4 time and features a melodic line in the treble clef with a long slur over a half note and a fermata. The piano accompaniment in the bass clef consists of eighth notes throughout.

33

p

36

C

f

39

f

tr

43

Musical score for measures 43-45. The top staff is empty. The middle staff (treble clef) features a trill (tr) on a dotted quarter note, followed by a sixteenth-note triplet, and another trill. The bottom staff (bass clef) has a rhythmic accompaniment of eighth notes with a flat (bb) and a quarter rest.

46

D

Musical score for measures 46-48. Measure 46 is marked with a box containing 'D'. The top staff (treble clef) has a melodic line with dynamics *mf*, *mp sub.*, and *mf*. The middle staff (treble clef) has a piano accompaniment with dynamics *p* and *mf*. The bottom staff (bass clef) has a rhythmic accompaniment with eighth notes and rests.

49

Musical score for measures 49-51. The top staff (treble clef) has a melodic line with dynamics *f* and *mf*. The middle staff (treble clef) has a piano accompaniment with dynamics *mf*. The bottom staff (bass clef) has a rhythmic accompaniment with eighth notes and rests.

52

mf *mp sub.* *mf*

p

55

f *ff* *f*

poco rit.....

58

mp *f*

p *mf*

E a tempo.

61

64

67

F

70

Musical score for measures 70-72. The piece is in 3/8 time, which changes to 4/4 time at measure 71. The right hand features a melodic line with eighth and sixteenth notes, while the left hand provides a rhythmic accompaniment with eighth notes and rests.

73

poco rit......

Musical score for measures 73-75. The tempo is marked *poco rit.* and the dynamics are *p*. The right hand has a melodic line with a slur over measures 74-75, and the left hand continues with a rhythmic accompaniment.

76

G a bit slower ♩ = 92

Musical score for measures 76-79. The tempo is marked **G** a bit slower with a quarter note equal to 92 (♩ = 92). The right hand has a melodic line with a slur over measures 77-78, and the left hand has a rhythmic accompaniment. The word *Red.* is written below the bass staff at the beginning and middle of the section.

80

Musical score for measures 80-83. The system consists of a vocal line and a piano accompaniment. The vocal line features a melodic phrase starting with a half note G4, followed by quarter notes A4, B4, and C5, then a half note B4, and finally a half note A4. The piano accompaniment has a treble clef with a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes and a bass clef with whole notes. The word "Ped." is written below the piano part in two locations.

84

Musical score for measures 84-87. The system consists of a vocal line and a piano accompaniment. The vocal line features a melodic phrase starting with a half note B4, followed by quarter notes C5, B4, and A4, then a half note G4, and finally a half note F4. The piano accompaniment has a treble clef with a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes and a bass clef with whole notes. The word "Ped." is written below the piano part in two locations.

88

Musical score for measures 88-91. The system consists of a vocal line and a piano accompaniment. The vocal line features a melodic phrase starting with a half note G4, followed by quarter notes A4, B4, and C5, then a half note B4, and finally a half note A4. The piano accompaniment has a treble clef with a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes and a bass clef with whole notes. The word "Ped." is written below the piano part in two locations.

91 H

(Red.)

95

5 6 3 3

99 I tempo I

104

f

mf

This system contains measures 104, 105, and 106. The music is in 7/8 time, which changes to 4/4 time in measure 105. The upper staff features a melodic line starting with a half rest in measure 104, followed by eighth and quarter notes. The lower staff provides accompaniment with chords and eighth notes. Dynamics include *f* and *mf*.

107

This system contains measures 107, 108, and 109. The time signature changes from 4/4 to 7/8 in measure 108. The upper staff has a melodic line with a long slur over the final two measures. The lower staff continues the accompaniment with chords and eighth notes.

110

f

This system contains measures 110, 111, and 112. The upper staff has a half rest in measure 110, followed by whole rests in measures 111 and 112. The lower staff provides accompaniment with chords and eighth notes. A dynamic of *f* is indicated in measure 111.

113 **J**

f

mf

116

mf

f

119 **K**

p

f

p

f

123

mp sub.

126

f sub. *mp sub.*

129

L

f sub.

132

f

mp

135

tr

f

molto rit. **M** Tempo I

138

ff

mf

141

Musical score for measures 141-143. The top staff is a single melodic line in treble clef. The bottom two staves are piano accompaniment in treble and bass clefs. The music starts in 3/8 time and changes to 4/4 time at measure 142. It features eighth and sixteenth notes with various accidentals and slurs.

144

Musical score for measures 144-146. The top staff has a long note with a fermata and a dynamic marking of *p*. The bottom two staves are piano accompaniment with a dynamic marking of *p*. The music is in 4/4 time.

147

Musical score for measures 147-150. The top staff has dynamic markings of *ff*, *fp*, and *fff*. It includes a trill (*tr*) and a fermata. The bottom two staves are piano accompaniment with a dynamic marking of *ff*. The music ends with a double bar line.